

THEORETICAL BASIS OF USING INTERACTIVE MEDIA RESOURCES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY

Ismailov Saidjon Azamjonovich

Senior teacher of the department of “Teaching Methods of Chemistry”

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Avazova Komila Erali qizi

3rd course student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Dangalova Adiba Amrillayevna

3rd course student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Annotation This article expresses possible options for using interactive media resources in the educational process of teaching chemistry. Interactive media resources contribute to the formation of students’ internal motivation to study chemistry, facilitate the search and transfer of information, make learning more visual, promote the use of an activity approach in the educational process and individualization of learning.

Key words: chemistry, media, interactive resource, theory, process, motivation, visual learning, resources

We live in an era of rapid change. Increasingly, on the way from theory to practice, there is not enough time to call innovations with adequate names and prevent confusion of related concepts. The “multimedia” arose even before the penetration of computers into everyday life and, initially, was associated with attempts to liken the communication of a person and an electronic computer to the perception of the real world through the flows of heterogeneous information - sound, visual, tactile, olfactory and gustatory.

In the works of G. Vernen, M. Shanon, I.L. Drizhun, A.A. Zhurina, V.V. Zagorsky, L.S. Zaznobina, O.S. Zaitseva, T.S. Nazarova, E. S. Polat, L.F.

Pleukhova, I.V. Robert, L.L. Chunikhina shows the possibilities of interactive media resources in the study of chemistry and other disciplines, highlights the most appropriate areas of their application from a methodological point of view.

In the studies of A.K. Akhlebinina, N.P. Bezrukova, G.Ya. Lastushkina, N.N. Pavlova, T.A. Sergeeva, S.G. Chaikova et al. considered the technique of using interactive media resources in the study of individual topics of the chemistry course.

As other subjects, there are several priorities of the use of interactive multimedia resources in chemistry. They are followings:

- Correct use of interactive multimedia resources opportunities of computer technologies in the education of chemistry creates condition for use of several channels of information at the same time. Learners see, hears training material and also is attracting to its mastering actively. These factors cause to increasing of mentality activity of pupils.
- Use of modern equipments in educational process changes the manner of mentality of learners completely on one hand and creates several conveniences for them on other hand: creates condition to save time spent for search of actual information, to get speed information by learners, decreases physical load of learner that is releases them from necessity to carry heavy books.
- Multimedia means help learners to achieve great successes in the education, students use techniques independently and believe in their successes.
- By getting ready didactic material, teachers achieve wide opportunities for application of new methodical ways in their lessons.
- The supply of the detailed information in a short period about chemical processes, which visual observation is impossible in the educational process, is provided.

By use of electron multimedia resources in the education of chemistry, students:

- observe chemical experiences by means of ICT, perceive topics easily;
- master to the abilities to use new information technologies for useful purposes;

- Observe some chemical reactions, which must be conducted in ventilating cases, master topics and are not associated with harmful substances being out of reaction.
- Observation of the course of chemical reactions by means of electron textbooks is very useful from ecological point of view. Because of harmful substances being out of reaction, especially gases do not pollute the weather.
- Students, who have speech defect and difficulties in summarizing and expressing his/her opinion, answer questions by means of computer and solve tasks.
- Students engage in animations and entertaining games given in electron textbook in free times, develop their knowledge and abilities and intellectual levels in chemistry.

There are several interactive multimedia resources in teaching chemistry. For example: “Umumiy kimyo”, “Kimyoviy formulalar tuzish”, “Chemistry Lab”, “Chemistry Lab equipment” va boshqalar.

Umumiy kimyo

Kimyoviy formulalar tuzish

Chemistry Lab

Chemistry Lab Equipment

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